

AIDAinnova

Advancement and Innovation for Detectors at Accelerators
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MILESTONE REPORT

DEFINITION OF SIPM REQUIREMENTS AND PERFORMANCE STUDIES WITH SIMULATIONS OF DIFFERENT USE CASES

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Abstract:

This report details the requirements of the photodetectors for the investigation of neutron resistant SiPM technology within the framework of the AIDAinnova programme. We discuss the recent different use cases, where the single photosensors are required. Finally, we give an overview of the performance simulations of application of such highly efficient sensors in the real environment.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2023

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Silicon photomultipliers are considered being one of the main candidates for the detection of single photons in future flavour physics experiments, where excellent particle identification is crucial to achieve their physics goals. They have a series of advantages over the other detectors, one of the main drawbacks is their sensitivity to neutron radiation.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the framework of AIDAinnova we are studying possibilities of using silicon photomultipliers as sensors of single photons in HEP experiments in highly irradiated environments. In the subtask 8.4.1 of WP8 we plan to identify main processes limiting their operation, and by using several design changes to improve their performance. We plan to find a usable operating range and recommendation for different use cases. In this document we identify the main requirements for the choice of photodetectors and report on the simulation studies showing the performance of particle identification for different use cases.

The present-day experiments in particle physics are searching for deviations from the Standard Model of elementary particles. In this search, experiments of the physics of heavy quark and lepton flavours form an important avenue. In fact, the study of possible deviations from lepton flavour universality is currently one of the hottest topics in high-energy physics. The two most important flavour physics experiments, currently under operation, are Belle II at the SuperKEKB collider of KEK, Tsukuba, Japan, and LHCb at the Large Hadron Collider of the European Organization for Nuclear Research – CERN, Geneva.

In both experiments, a reliable charged particle identification is of paramount importance, and Ring Imaging Cherenkov detectors are employed for this task. Ring Imaging Cherenkov counters (RICH) rely on the property of charged particles to emit Cherenkov photons at a particular angle, depending on the particle's velocity. RICH detectors detect single Cherenkov photons and then measure their characteristic emission angle with respect to the charged particle direction. This measurement makes it possible to reconstruct the particle velocity and, combined with the measured momentum, infer its mass – and thus its identity.

In the LHCb experiment, focusing RICH detectors are used with gas-based Cherenkov radiators, spherical mirrors, and multi-anode photomultipliers as photosensors. In the Belle II experiment, a proximity focusing type RICH with aerogel radiator and hybrid avalanche photodetectors is used in the endcap, and a Time-Of-Propagation (TOP) counter with quartz radiator is employed in the barrel part.

2. REQUIREMENTS

In the LHCb the multi-anode PMTs are currently used for the detection of single photons. In Belle II, both particle identification devices are located inside a magnet with a 1.5T magnetic field, in the aerogel RICH the Hybrid avalanche photodetectors are used, while in the case of Time-Of-Propagation counter, the MCP-PMTs attached to the quartz bars are responsible for the measurement of the single photon position and the arrival time. Around 30 detected photons per track are needed

for an efficient separation in the LHCb RICH, and around 10 in the Belle II RICH; the difference between the two is mainly due to the different track densities impacting the background in the distributions.

To increase the size of the data sample of recorded events available for studies of rare processes, the next generation of experiments is under preparation with a much higher interaction density. For example, with the upgrade of the Large Hadron Collider (High Luminosity LHC Upgrade), the collider will deliver **50 times higher instantaneous luminosity** than the present one. For the operation under considerable higher particle fluxes produced in collisions, the upgrade of the detectors will be necessary. For the LHCb Upgrade II during the Long Shutdown 4, the upgrade is foreseen to enable detector capabilities during Run 5 [1]. At Belle II, an upgrade of the machine and detector is being discussed [2], again to reach higher luminosities, resulting in higher event rates, and higher irradiation levels of the spectrometer components.

Figure 1: Two flavour physics experiments where the use of highly granular, radiation resistant single photon light sensors will be crucial during the foreseen upgrades – LHCb (left) and Belle II (right).

One of the most critical problems in the LHCb RICH after the High Luminosity LHC upgrade is the photosensor channel **occupancy**, which will, in the case of **currently used $3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$ channels**, **exceed 130%** close to the beam pipe and hence dramatically decrease the particle identification efficiency. One solution to **reduce the occupancy** is **a finer granularity of the photosensors**. This modification will, in addition, improve the resolution for the measurement of the Cherenkov angle, which also affects the identification efficiency. Improving the angular resolutions require also shifting the photon detection range in the visible wavelengths and minimizing optical distortions. These represent a complete paradigm shift for gaseous RICH detector techniques.

Another problem after the luminosity upgrade of LHC is the **event pile-up**. By measuring the arrival time of individual photons in the RICH1 with a **time resolution** better than **200 ps**, we could substantially **mitigate** this problem.

For efficient particle identification in these extreme environments, we therefore need a **photosensor** with a **granularity** of about **one mm^2** , **high efficiency** for detecting single **photons with wavelength beyond 400 nm**, a high gain, and a **good time resolution** of about 200 ps. In addition, also the photon detector should be able to **operate in a magnetic field** and withstand an equivalent **neutron fluence** of about **$3 \times 10^{13} \text{ n/cm}^2$** . The requirements for the upgrade of the Belle II aerogel RICH are less stringent: the expected fluence is about 10 times lower, the photosensor channel occupancy will be much smaller, and the required granularity is about 5 mm x 5 mm. In the case of the Time-Of-Propagation detector the expected fluence is even one magnitude lower, the main obstacle is that

sensors will have to be in contact with the quartz bars. In all the cases, a stable operation of the photosensors is crucial.

Only a few photosensor types are suitable candidates for the detection of single photons in such a demanding environment. The most promising is the **silicon photomultiplier (SiPM)**, an avalanche photodiode operating in the Geiger mode and enabling the detection of single photons with high efficiency. This sensor type has **high efficiency for detecting single photons**, high gain, **good time resolution**, can work in a magnetic field and is operated at low bias voltages from 20V to 80V.

However, before this sensor can be employed, additional research is needed. One issue with these sensors is the required **reduction of the background hits** caused by the thermal generation of electron-hole pairs. The even bigger issue is the **neutron sensitivity** since the bulk damage in silicon due to neutron irradiation becomes another source of background.

Silicon photomultipliers have been strongly improved in the last years. Crosstalk between pixels has been strongly reduced with the introduction of the “trench” technique, after pulses have been suppressed using new substrates, radiation hardness has been improved implementing the new techniques inside micro-cells of silicon photomultipliers. The goal of this work package task is to study, evaluate and define operating parameters of silicon photomultipliers and to test their operation under neutron irradiation to boost the development of radiation-hard silicon photomultipliers. First milestone in this task is the identification of the requirements. We studied them and collected the most important ones in Table 1.

Application / Property	Unit	TOP at Belle II	Aerogel RICH at Belle II	RICH at LHCb
Sensor size	mm ²	3x3	5x5	1x1 – 3x3
Single photon sensitivity	%	required	required	required
Low DCR ¹		required	required	required
Required Peak PDE		Blue	Blue	Green
Single photon timing resolution	ps	50	100	100
Operating temperature	°C	20 ²	In the range from -20 to 20	-100 ³
Light focusing		Not possible ⁴	Yes	Yes
Area to cover	m ²	0.4	4.5	0.5-3.7 ⁵

¹ High dark count rate can distort the signal baseline

Area to cover

² Thermal contact with quartz bars makes low material budget cooling infrastructure challenging, if not impossible

³ Gas vessel should be above the boiling point of C4F10 gas (-1.7 °C)

⁴ A wide angular acceptance is needed

⁵ The highest occupancy region covers only limited detector area. Depending on the achieved performance and cost, silicon photomultipliers might be used to detect single photons on those hottest part of the photon detector, while the less populated areas might be read out with MAPMTs.

Neutron Fluence 1MeV eq.	n/cm ²	10 ¹¹	10 ¹²	3x10 ¹³
Trigger rate	kHz	30	30	40000
Photon incident angle	°	0-90	0-30	0-10
Start of Operation		2034-	2034-	2034-

Table 1. Performance requirements for photo sensors of the Time of Propagation Counter and Aerogel RICH at Belle II and RICH at LHCb

Sensor size: The required granularity of the photo sensor depends on the other optical components of the photon detection system and is chosen in coherence with the other contributions to the measurement error. The important parameter is the sensor sensitive area from which the photons are collected.

Single photon sensitivity: In the particle identification systems, only few photons are detected. It is crucial that they are detected with high efficiency. In the case of Cherenkov radiation, the photons impact on different parts of the detector plane. The probability that more than one photon hits the single sensitive channel is small, therefore the detection at the single photon level is important.

Low DCR: In RICH, the photon emission time is very correlated with the bunch crossing time of the colliding beams. However, the probability for a random coincidence window is rising with increasing dark count rate. In addition, due to pile up effects a signal baseline can be distorted. It has been shown that the single photon resolution is lost above certain level of DCR.

Required peak PDE: Due to chromatic dispersion, the sensitivity towards red is preferred. Unfortunately, due to $1/\lambda^2$ dependence of the emission spectrum of the emitted light, the number of emitted photons strongly decreases and a compromise should be determined on a case-by-case basis.

Single photon timing resolution: For good particle identification performance, an excellent timing performance is required for the time of propagation counter. In LHCb RICH the good timing performance is needed to attribute photons to the tracks arising from different primary vertices.

Operating temperature: The operating temperature requirement arises from the complexity of the cooling system. In the case of LHCb RICH, the photo detector plane is positioned outside the particle flux and does not interfere with the energy measurement. If needed and carefully designed, the cooling system can cool the sensors (and possibly the electronics down to liquid nitrogen levels). In the case of Belle II, both detectors are positioned in front of the electromagnetic calorimeter, use of the cooling system is very limited. The Time of propagation counter has an additional drawback that the sensors are in thermal contact with the radiator quartz bars.

Light focusing, photon incidence angle: Light is in the case of Cherenkov detectors emitted in the limited angle, contrary to the scintillation light. The directionality enables the design of the focusing elements which collect the light from larger area and focus it to smaller sensitive regions.

Area to cover: Total required coverage depends on the experiment design. In the LHCb RICH the highest occupancy regions amount to about 1 m².

Trigger rate: In the case of LHCb RICH, where the triggerless configuration is envisaged, all the events will be transferred to an online processing farm for data reduction, whereas in the case of Belle II, the trigger is determined by the other subsystems based on the event topology.

Neutron fluence: This is the most important optimisation parameter, that will be addressed within this AIDAInnova task.

Electronics: The current LHCb RICH consists of the RICH1 detector upstream and the RICH2 detector downstream of the LHCb magnet (see Figure 1). The RICH1 C4F10 radiator has a kaon low-momentum threshold at 10 GeV/c, while the RICH2 CF4 radiator covers the higher momentum range with good π -K separation up to 100 GeV. The RICH system for the future LHCb detector will be a natural evolution of the current detectors. During Long Shutdown 4 (LS4), currently scheduled for 2033, the LHCb detector will undergo a major overhaul called Upgrade II to be able to maintain its excellent performance at the high luminosity during Run 5, a factor 7.5 increase in luminosity with respect to Run 3 and 4, with the aim of integrating 300 fb⁻¹ throughout the HL-LHC era. To prepare for the change the RICH detector will have to be upgraded in several steps. One of the major improvements will be the recording of the time. The time measurement is foreseen to be performed by a new ASIC FastRICH, based on the FastIC family of the chips (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Gradual upgrades toward the high luminosity LHC Upgrade.

A novel ASIC (FastRICH) and a direct connection to the newly developed optical links components (lpGBT/VL+) has the capability to gate the acquisition to about 2 ns (and not 25 ns of the LHC crossing rate) and to provide each photon detected inside this gate with a precise timestamp by using a TDC with readout bins of 25 ps. This results in a time resolution of 150 ps, limited only by the sensor transient time spread. The same ASIC is planned to be integrated in the LHCb Upgrade II RICH.

3. PION IDENTIFICATION PERFORMANCE

The effects of different timings and different detector backgrounds were simulated using the Geant4 based LHCb and Belle II detector simulations with the current reconstruction tools. In the detector simulations, the detector geometry has been properly described, so that the generated interactions of particles with matter are consistent with the measurements for the current environments.

LHCb RICH Identification performance

The performance has been simulated using the LHCb simulation is based on the LHCb Simulation software, built on the Gaudi Framework by adjusting the granularity and sensitivity of the RICH photon detector using the $1 \times 1 \text{ mm}^2$ large channels with a photon detection efficiency corresponding to the FBK HD-NUV silicon photomultipliers. In the current particle identification algorithms, the arrival time has not been included yet, therefore only the effect of different time gating windows has been studied. The most occupied part of the LHCb RICH detector is the central area of $40 \times 40 \text{ cm}^2$ while the outer regions have lower occupancy (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Channel occupancy of the LHCb RICH1 during the Run5. The occupancy was calculated for $1 \times 1 \text{ mm}^2$ large channels.

The effect of using sensors with different timing resolution / gating capabilities is shown in Figure 4. Note the increase of efficiency at the same level of pion mis-identification probability with decreasing sensor time-gating. The requirement for a good timing resolution is one of the key performance requirements.

Figure 4: Kaon identification efficiency versus pion mis-identification probability for the LHCb RICH1. Effect of different sensor timing resolution (gate) is shown.

Belle II

In the case of Belle II aerogel RICH, performance parameters have been simulated for different levels of the expected background. The generic Monte Carlo event generator was used for the generation of interactions and the detector response has been simulated using the Basf2 – Belle II Analysis and Simulation framework. The standard particle identification algorithms were used for the identification of the particles [3]. They are based on the construction of the two-dimensional extended likelihood function evaluated for different particle hypotheses. From the likelihoods the K identification efficiency and pion mis-identification probability has been extracted. It can be seen that at 1 GeV/c momentum the identification performance at 5% pion mis-identification probability drops of about 2% if the background is increased for a factor of 5 and for about 7% if the background increase factor is 10. For higher momenta the drop is even smaller - 2% in the case of 10 times background increase with respect to the nominal one.

Figure 5: Kaon identification efficiency versus pion mis-identification probability for particles with a momentum of 1 GeV/c (left) and 4 GeV/c (right) for the Belle II ARICH.

To conclude, the performance simulations show that the silicon photomultipliers can be a viable candidate for detection of single photons.

4. REFERENCES

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ANNEX: GLOSSARY

	Definition
MAPMT	Multi anode photomultiplier
MCP-PMT	Micro channel plate PMT
HAPD	Hybrid avalanche photodetector
SiPM	Silicon photomultiplier
ASIC	Application specific integrated Circuit
LHC	Large Hadron Collider
TDC	Time to digital converter
FastIC	Low power multichannel ASIC enabling energy and timing measurements, developed in collaboration between CERN and University of Barcelona
FastRICH	Variation of FastIC, which will include the TDC
RICH	Ring Imaging Cherenkov detector
ARICH	RICH with a silica aerogel radiator
DCR	Dark count rate